

Condensation of *m*-Halogeno-phenols with Acetone-Dicarboxylic Acid in presence of Sulphuric Acid

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From the reaction product of *m*-halogeno-phenols with acetone dicarboxylic acid in presence of sulphuric acid, 7-halogeno-coumarin-4-acetic acids and $\beta\beta$ -bis-(4-halogeno-phenyl)glutaro-lactones have been isolated.

Phenols, naphthols, and their ethers are well known for the ease with which these condense with acetone dicarboxylic acid in presence of condensing agents like H_2SO_4 ; the resulting products are coumarin-4-acetic acids¹, β -arylglytaconic acids², $\beta\beta$ -diarylglutaric acids³, and $\beta\beta$ -bis-(phenyl)glutaro-lactones⁴.

m-Halogeno-phenols, prepared from *m*-nitroaniline, were condensed with acetone dicarboxylic acid in presence of H_2SO_4 . A part of the condensation product was found soluble in a solution of $NaHCO_3$ (A) and a part insoluble in it (B). On decarboxylation of (A), 4-methyl-7-halogeno-coumarins (II) were formed as proved by mixed melting points with specimens of 4-methyl-7-halogeno-coumarins prepared from 4-methyl-7-aminocoumarin⁵. The products (A) therefore should be 7-halogeno-coumarin-4-acetic acids (I).

The non-acidic compounds (B), on hydrolysis with caustic alkali, afforded 7-halogeno-coumarin-4-acetic acids (I) and *m*-halogeno-phenols. These compounds were therefore formulated as $\beta\beta$ -bis-(4-halogeno-phenyl)glutaro-lactones (III).

1. Pechmann, *Annalen*, 1899, **281**, 167; Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 1505; Limaye, *this Journal*, 1927, **4**, 159.
2. Limaye and Dixit, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1930, Part III, 167.
3. Dixit and Gokhale, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1934, **3**, 80; *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1932, Part III, 225; Gogate, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1937, **5A**, 535.
4. Dixit, *this Journal*, 1945, **22**, 207.
5. Subbarao and Sundermurthy, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1956, **33A**, 149.

TABLE I

Compounds.	Cryst. from.	%Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.		Equivalen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1. I (X=Br)	60% EtOH	5	198° (d)	C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₄ Br	48.71	49.65	2.41	2.47	281.3	283
2. Anilide of (1)	Do	..	130°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ NBr	56.83	56.98	3.20	3.35	..	..
3. II (X=Br)	..	..	*136°	..	..	..	..	..	..	..
4. III (X=Br)	EtOH (light yellow shining needles)	..	> 300°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₄ Br ₂	..	..	..	..	..	..
5. IV (X=Br)	Gl. AcOH (soft white needles)..	> 256°	> 300°	C ₁₈ H ₉ O ₄ Br	58.01	58.55	2.22	2.44	..	..
6. I (X=I)	60% EtOH	4	178° (d)	C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₄ I	38.02	40.00	1.94	2.12	332.8	330
7. Anilide of (6)	50% EtOH (brownish needles)	..	155°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ NI	50.08	50.38	2.65	2.96	..	..
8. Mesomer of (6)	30% AcOH (colorless light needles)	..	142°	C ₁₂ H ₉ C ₄ I	41.59	41.86	2.51	2.62	..	..
9. II (X=I)	..	..	157°	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₄ I	41.76	41.96	2.36	2.45	..	..
10. III (X=I)	EtOH (light brown needles)	2.5	> 300°	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₄ I ₂	38.03	38.34	1.82	1.88	..	..
11. IV (X=I)	Gl. AcOH (soft light needles)	..	275°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₄ I	51.74	51.51	2.06	2.16	..	..

* Undepressed m. p. with an authentic sample.

† Hydrolysis with 20% NaOH soln. furnishes bromo isomer of (1) and *m*-bromophenol.
(d) decomposes.

EXPERIMENTAL

7-Chlorocoumarin-4-acetic Acid (I: X=Cl).—*m*-Chlorophenol (9.75 g.) was added to acetone dicarboxylic acid, prepared from citric acid (25 g.), and H_2SO_4 (conc., 40 ml). The mixture was heated for 6 hours at 60° and then kept overnight. The reaction mass was poured over crushed ice when a solid separated.

A part of the solid (A) dissolved in $NaHCO_3$ solution with effervescence and a part (B) remained insoluble. The bicarbonate solution on acidification provided a solid which was crystallised from dilute ethanol in fine needles, m.p. 206° (decomp.), yield 5%. (Found: C, 55.19; H, 3.08; equiv., 237.7. $C_{11}H_9O_4Cl$ requires C, 55.35; H, 2.93%; equiv., 238.5).

7-Chloro-4-methylcoumarin (II: X=Cl).—The above acid was heated at 215° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The solid formed was sublimed under reduced pressure; m.p. 144°. Mixed m.p. with a sample of 4-methyl-7-chlorocoumarin³ showed no depression.

Anilide of 7-chlorocoumarin-4-acetic acid was crystallised from dilute ethanol. m.p. 145°. (Found: C, 64.62; H, 3.85. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3NCl$ requires C, 65.07; H, 3.82%).

Methyl ester of 7-chlorocoumarin-4-acetic acid crystallised from 30% acetic acid, m.p. 112°. (Found: C, 56.90; H, 3.50. $C_{12}H_9O_4Cl$ requires C, 57.02; H, 3.56%).

$\beta\beta$ -Bis-(4-chlorophenyl)glutaro-lactone (III: X=Cl).—The non-acidic substance (B) was crystallised from ethanol in reddish shining plates, m.p. above 300°. This compound on hydrolysis with 20% NaOH solution furnished 7-chlorocoumarin-4-acetic acid (I: X=Cl) and *m*-chlorophenol. (Found: C, 58.38; H, 2.79. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4Cl_2$ requires C, 58.45; H, 2.86%).

7-Chloro-4,3'-dicoumaryl (IV: X=Cl).—To the methyl ester of 7-chlorocoumarin-4-acetic acid (1g.), dissolved in the least quantity of absolute ethanol, salicylaldehyde (0.5 g.) and piperidine (3 drops) were added and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hours. The resulting solid was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in soft white needles, m.p. 253°. (Found: C, 66.42; H, 2.85. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4Cl$ requires C, 66.61; H, 2.77%).

All bromo and iodo compounds were prepared like their chloro isomers. Analytical data, m. p., yield, and other characteristics of the iodo and bromo compounds are recorded in Table I.

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